

NDC ASPECTS

Sectoral Conversations Guidebook (Deliverable 1.4)

WP1 – Sectoral Conversations

Lukas Hermwille, Anna Pérez Català, Willington Ortiz,
Marta Torres Gunfaus, Meike Spitzner

Wuppertal Institute & IDDRI

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Sectoral Conversations Guidebook

Lukas Hermwille	Wuppertal Institute
Lukas.hermwille@wupperist.org	https://wupperinst.org/
Anna Pérez Català	IDDRI
anna.perezcatala@iddri.org	https://www.iddri.org/
Marta Torres Gunfaus	IDDRI
marta.torres-gunfaus@iddri.org	https://www.iddri.org/
Willington Ortiz	Wuppertal Institute
willington.ortiz@wupperist.org	https://wupperinst.org/
Meike Spitzner	Wuppertal Institute
meike.spitzner@wupperist.org	https://wupperinst.org/

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Executive Summary

The purpose of the Sectoral Conversations is to provide a space for inter- and transdisciplinary exchange within the project and with project-external sectoral experts. It provides an opportunity to share (interim) results from the outset with different disciplines and external stakeholders. Their feedback might help to hone research questions and reconfigure ongoing analyses so that they speak to each other, thus maximizing their policy and academic relevance.

This deliverable is a guidebook to support the successful implementation of the Sectoral Conversations for industry, mobility & transport, buildings, and agriculture, land use and forestry under the NDC ASPECTS project. First, it serves to underpin the theoretical and conceptual basis for common understanding in the Sectoral Conversations by introducing key terms and concepts including: sectoral systems, sectoral conversations, triangulation, decarbonisation narratives as well as gender responsiveness.

Moreover, the deliverable describes the generic process of the Sectoral Conversations each of which contains three main conversation cycles as well as a preparatory and a cross-sectoral synthesis phase. Each of the cycles again contains the preparation, implementation and digest of the conversation encounter. The guidebook highlights that are of particular importance at the various stages. To organize and facilitate these processes, the document introduces the concept of process design documents (PDDs). For each of the four Sectoral Conversations, a PDD will be maintained to prepare the Conversation encounters, document key results – both in terms of content and process lessons – and digest/debrief them. The PDDs will be key inputs for the development of a methodological research article. They are intended as living documents and will be continuously revised and developed during the project duration. The current version of the PDDs for all four Sectoral Conversations are included as an annex in the deliverable.

Moreover, this guidebook contains practical recommendations for the researchers implementing and moderating the Sectoral Conversations. It includes short instructions for various engagement methods to facilitate transdisciplinary exchange. So far, the toolkit includes instructions for the methods “conceptual clarification”, “three horizons dialogue”, and “futures wheel”, all of which are particularly suitable for early stages of transdisciplinary research processes. It is intended to expand this section to further support the leads of the Sectoral Conversations towards the second and third conversation cycle. The final section includes practical recommendations in relation to the administration and logistics of the Sectoral Conversation encounters.

This deliverable also provides the foundations for a project glossary. To date, it only contains a small number of entries (narratives, pathways, model, decarbonization, sectoral system, sector coupling, transdisciplinarity, transformation). Again, it is intended to expand and maintain the glossary throughout the project duration as a resource for the project in general and the Sectoral Conversations in particular.

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1 Introduction

The purpose of the Sectoral Conversations is to provide a **space for inter- and transdisciplinary exchange within the project and with project-external sectoral experts**. It provides an opportunity to share (interim) results from the outset with different disciplines and external stakeholders. Their feedback might help to hone research questions and reconfigure ongoing analyses so that they speak to each other, thus maximizing their policy and academic relevance.

The Sectoral Conversations shall encourage an open and transparent research process in a trustful environment. It should NOT constrain research in any of the subsequent work packages. Nor should the other work packages focus their research activities exclusively on providing inputs to the Sectoral Conversations.

The purpose of this guidebook is to support the sectoral leads in organizing the Sectoral Conversations in a way that stimulates exchange between different disciplines within the NDC ASPECTS consortium and external participants, in order to help us discover and exploit synergies between our respective research activities.

The guidebook is structured in seven sections. After this introduction, we first introduce a selection of key terms and concepts that are the foundation of our Sectoral Conversation. Section 3 introduces the general concept of the Sectoral Conversations (SC) and how they ought to be structured. Subsequently, we provide guidance for the Sectoral Leads in charge of the implementation of the Sectoral Conversations on how to develop the groundwork for a successful implementation, including by pre-scoping the thematic focus of the SCs as well as considerations on the involvement of stakeholders. Section 5, then, can be seen as a cookbook of engagement methods that can be selected by the sectoral teams as they see fit. Work on this section will be continued throughout the project, taking into account the needs of the four Sectoral Conversations and the experiences made in the first engagement cycles. Section six contains operational guidance on the implementation and administration of the Sectoral Conversations. This guidebook concludes with a glossary – again intended as a living document – as a place to settle terminological disputes and record important working definitions as they arise during the implementation of the NDC ASPECTS project in general and the Sectoral Conversations in particular.

2 Key Terms and Concepts

This section provides an overview of key scientific concepts and terms as they apply to the project. The discussion provided represents not necessarily a definitive discussion of the term but reflects the intended use of the terms in this project. Alongside with the glossary at the end of this guidebook, this section is therefore a point of reference and resource for the entire project, the groundwork for our common language across disciplines and sectors.

2.1 Sectoral System

The following discussion is cited from Oberthür, S., Hermwille, L., & Rayner, T. (2021). A sectoral perspective on global climate governance: Analytical foundation. Earth System Governance, 8, 100104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esg.2021.100104>:

According to transition theory (see also Victor et al., 2019) sectoral systems provide identifiable societal functions such as transport, electricity, or raw materials for industrial production. They are constituted of ensembles of actors (corporations, administrative bodies, political groups/parties, international organizations), technologies and infrastructures, economic structures, institutions and ideas that produce degrees of path dependency and resistance to change (Geels & Schot, 2010). Such systems are complex, which entails that (1) they can produce emergent phenomena/effects that are more than the systems' parts, and (2) they are open, i.e. closely related to and potentially overlapping and interdependent with other sectoral systems (Page, 2011). Our societies and economies are supported by a patchwork of such socio-technological systems. Their number tends to increase with the advancing functional differentiation of modern societies, which also entails that sectoral systems might be further subdivided into various overlapping sectoral subsystems. For example, relevant transport sub-sectors include land transport (by train, car, others), sea/water transport, air transport, passenger transport, freight transport, international transport (aviation and maritime), urban transport, etc. As this example indicates, sectoral systems can easily overlap (e.g., urban transport and passenger/freight transport) (Borrás & Edler, 2014; Harich, 2010; Page, 2011; Schot & Kanger, 2018; Unruh, 2000).

2.2 Sectoral Conversations

There is increasing consensus that cooperation between scientists from different disciplines and actors from outside academia is needed in order to deal with the urgent sustainability challenges faced by the modern global world (Bammer, 2005; Hirsch Hadorn et al., 2008; Jahn & Keil, 2012; Scholz, 2000).

A key challenge for the NDC ASPECTS project is to advance the knowledge articulation across the different epistemic cultures, levels and scales that have to be necessarily addressed by transformative dynamics towards the deep decarbonization of the four considered sectors. Systematic articulation among diversity of knowledge and knowledge conditions is crucial for the overarching goal of the project to provide cutting-edge analysis and robust scientific evidence in support of the 2023 Global Stocktake. This will enhance the social and cultural robustness of the generated knowledge, i.e. knowledge that can be understood, processed and applied by all parties involved (Nowotny et al., 2001), and knowledge accounting for uncertainties and the ambiguities linked to it (Vilsmaier, 2008):

- › to orchestrate the different disciplinary pieces of analysis for each of the sectors so that they relate to each other in a synergistic way;

- › to co-design the research questions, co-produce results, and co-create specific recommendations;
- › to facilitate the results' implementation and exploitation and hence the project impact;
- › and to build common options and visions among the participants of the sectoral community further facilitating the materialization of present NDCs and increasing the ambition of future ones.

The Sectoral Conversations are conceived as a series of sector-specific transdisciplinary mutual learning formats among a small, but targeted and carefully selected group of NDC ASPECTS researchers and external stakeholders within a sectoral system that co-produce knowledge and builds relationships over the project lifetime. The Sectoral Conversations enable us to combine interdisciplinary work with deep stakeholder involvement throughout the entire project. They provide a space to explore the complementarities and contradictions of different disciplinary perspectives. A focus will be put on the triangulation of results from the various research inputs coming from the project (see below).

2.3 Triangulation

Triangulation is commonly understood as the application of different methods/approaches/perspectives on the same or a very similar issue with a view to mutually validate research results. This approach can also be described as 'triangulation for convergence'. However, triangulation may also be used to broaden the understanding of the subject matter – 'triangulation for complementarity' (Huntington et al., 2004). Finally, 'triangulation for divergence' can be employed to "reveal the mismatches between scales of knowledge of the actors, i.e., scientists, government officials, and citizens, involved." (Ahlborg & Nightingale, 2012, p. 16).

2.4 Decarbonisation narrative

The following description of the concept "decarbonisation narrative" is based on the results of a "conceptual clarification" exercise (see Section 5 of this guideline) that was undertaken on 29 July 2021 as part of the Kick-off meeting of the WP1. This concept was selected for that exercise because of its relevance for advancing the objectives of supporting transformative dynamics towards the deep decarbonisation of the four considered sectors. This section reports on: (a) issues in which common understanding among the participant researchers was apparent, (b) issues that remained unclear or controversial and (c) the roles that decarbonisation narratives can have in the different research strands of the project.

2.4.1 Pieces of common understanding

Decarbonisation narratives can be understood as stories that describe how deep reductions in the GHG emissions of a sectoral system could be achieved. These stories are built of elements such as:

- › The **drivers** of current emissions as well as of potential reductions
- › The **conditions** that determine the current performance of the sectoral systems as well as the possibilities for inducing changes towards decarbonising them

- › The **actors** that are key in order to advance the transformation of the sectoral systems and/or that would result particularly affected by the transformation
- › The **strategies** that those actors can apply in order to effectively advance the decarbonisation of the sectoral systems
- › The (additional) **impacts** that the envisioned transformation might bring about to societies and economies in general; i.e. effects (positive and negative) beyond the reduction of GHG emissions.

2.4.2 Unclear or controversial issues

Three issues appear of relevance for characterizing what “decarbonisation narratives” are in the frame of the NDC-ASPECTS project, but remained unclear or controversial after the conceptual clarification exercise:

- › Differentiation to other types of ‘stories’: Other terms such as ‘storylines’, ‘pathways’ and ‘scenarios’ are commonly used in academic and political debates on climate mitigation. All those terms also refer to ways of ‘telling stories’ about how climate mitigation can look like in the future. The scope of the exercise did not allow for exploring the differences and relations among those other types of ‘story-telling’.
- › The purpose: One approach is to understand decarbonisation narratives as a methodological tool that can facilitate the articulation and integration of results from different strands of analysis (project-internal purpose). For instance by providing consistency and coherence in the assumptions set for different types of analysis. On the other hand, decarbonisation narratives can be understood as tools for facilitating the transfer of the results of the research to a broad range of (non-academic) audiences (project-external purpose). For instance by translating results emanating from complex sets of assumptions, models and/or analyses into rather straightforward stories about the decarbonisation process.
- › Multiplicity: Given the different system boundaries that are being considered by the different research strands of the project (i.e. sectors, national states, geographical regions) it can be expected that the elements of the stories about their transformations can vary from one system to the other. Linked to this issue is the question to which extent it is possible or meaningful to strive for building/finding one “all embracing” (global) narrative that unifies all system-specific narratives, or is able to set them in relation.

2.4.3 Roles in the analytical processes

Some of the unclear or controversial issues found during the conceptual clarification exercise point at two usages or roles that decarbonisation narratives can have in different research strands of the project.

- › Inputs for the research process: Decarbonisation narratives can be understood as qualitative descriptions of *plausible* future developments of the sectoral systems. In this way they can provide a starting point for deriving and/or underpinning specific assumptions and parameters needed to run the analysis about those plausible futures. This role of decarbonisation narratives as inputs for the research process is characteristic of analysis comprising quantitative modelling and simulation methods.
- › Outputs from the research process: Decarbonisation narratives can be also understood as qualitative descriptions of how the transformation process of sectoral systems can be expected to take place. In this vein they can serve as formats for elaborating theories of changes that synthesize insights derived from diverse types of sources and analyses. This kind of usage can be particularly interesting for combining insights from existing evidence (e.g., on the transformation effects of policy instruments or technical innovations) with quantitative and qualitative projections of future trajectories.

2.5 Gender Responsiveness

The project work will follow the European Union's Gender Mainstreaming's requirements of every sector's/action field's actively improving gender equality (European Commission, 1996, 2005, 2015). Gender mainstreaming is the (re)organization, improvement, development and evaluation of policy processes, so that a gender equality perspective is incorporated in all policies, at all levels and at all stages, by the actors normally involved in policy-making.

The project also refers to the UNFCCC enhanced Lima work programme on gender (LWPG) and its gender action plan (UNFCCC GenderAP), and to the institutionalization of gender responsiveness in the project's technical contexts (Obergassel et al., 2021) such as NDC Partnership Gender Strategy (NDC Partnership, 2019), the initiative by the European Capacity Building Initiative towards 'International gender commitments to national action - Integrating gender in climate change (Granat et al., 2020), and in implementing gender responsiveness in discussing methods for assessing impacts of response measures (UNFCCC, 2021) as well as to UNFCCC parties, who subject their national climate strategies to an analysis of how these should be systematically revised so that they comply with the UN, EU and national gender mainstreaming requirements of active professional climate policy contributions to improving gender equality in society, like e.g. Germany (Spitzner et al., 2020).

The project implements gender-responsiveness by systematically applying the seven gender dimensions of the problem oriented ex-ante gender impact assessment (GIA) (Spitzner, 2021b) as categories of analysis in the technical context of sectors and of country-specific data collection and climate policies analysis.

2.5.1 Meaning of Gender

Gender refers to the historical formation and the political and societal changeability of gender roles. A specific binary system of characteristics, responsibilities, and meanings are structurally ascribed to these gender roles or deprived of them. This results in structural gender relationships in society associated with unequal opportunities and burdens. This focus on imposed gender roles contrasts with and must not be confused with biological sex.

Gender is a structural category of society. By means of a predominant social structuring principle, men and women are positioned in the hierarchies created by gender relations (Hofmeister & Mölders, 2006). For this reason, societal gender relations, inequality situations for women, other genders and men and their diversity, their conditions and the reduction of these inequalities must be addressed.

Gender is also a process category. In social and organizational situations of interaction, gender in the sense of “doing gender” is continuously produced in an active interpersonal and institutional way. Men, women and other genders are confronted with powerful and structural binary masculinity-femininity ascriptions and stereotypes (today even more intensified by digitalisation); they have to deal with them in one way or another. Either, they can adapt to the stereotype characteristics, behaviour patterns, attitudes, preferences, etc. of these societally ascribed attributions in individually different proportions. Or they can resist them and create counter realities to the binary institutionalization of gender. However, the latter often comes at the price of increased struggle and a risk of marginalization.

Gender refers to the relationships between what is societally ascribed to masculinity and what is societally ascribed to femininity. Structural gender inequality is marked by the fact that association with constructed masculinity is given priorities, primacy and privileges in political, economic, infrastructural, institutional, planning a.o. powerful rationalities. Meanwhile, femininity is frequently and implicitly considered subordinate. For instance, many aspects of life that are not profitably exploitable are being externalised from masculinity and attributed to femininity (cf. the actual overview on these findings originating from the last decades and deepened for actual European climate strategies until today in Spitzner, 2021a). The central challenge pertains to how these societal gender constructions and gender relationships are associated with social, political and economic inequalities, exclusions, and definition- and shaping power relationships and how to overcome these.

Despite some advances towards gender equality, societies in general and policymaking in particular are still predominantly viewed and organized from a perspective where a constructed model of masculinity, e.g. the full-time working family breadwinner, is seen as the norm (in spite of being a marginal minority perspective, deviating from perspectives of majority of societies, even of boys, old men and men who do not want to or cannot follow this version of masculinity), as benchmark for (scientific) “objectivity”, for (political) “general interest” and as representative concern of all genders. For example, the term “work” and related economic accounting in the gender-blind mainstream usually refers exclusively to paid work and does not include unpaid reproductive and care work within and between households, which is still predominantly externalised from masculinity and undertaken by women. Studies have shown that the hourly volume of unpaid reproductive and care work actually exceeds the volume of paid work; still, the responsibility for this societies’ basic economic sector is largely absent from economic and political discourse and policy. Such implicit fixation of political, economic, scientific and technological ‘rationalities’ on (models of) masculinity as structural benchmark is referred to as “androcentrism”.

2.5.2 Climate Relevance of Gender

Gender-based inequalities are of high relevance for climate policy in many respects.

For example, public transport systems are usually focused on enabling mobility of paid labour, to bring employees from their homes in the urban outskirts to work in the city centres in the morning and back home in the evening, according to the only masculine “standard working hours”. Serving the trips that

are necessary for part-time paid work as well as for care work, such as bringing children to kindergarten/school, visiting the doctor, shopping for groceries, etc. are not systematically cared for and not given any priority in the focus of transport policy and public transport planning. Households are therefore often forced to either undertake long roundabout, time-intensive trips by public transport - undermining the potential for income generating work/ security of independent economic and existential independence - or to motorize, with its associated GHG emissions. Moreover, vehicles are charged with symbolic meaning based on gender-based masculine affinities for being highly engineered, for high speed, for long distances, for overcoming spatial bindings, overlooking respective dependencies on the care economy. This contributes to disproportionate political prioritization of motorized car infrastructure systems over public and non-motorized transport networks and services, which are more environmentally friendly as well as care economically and socially adequate (Spitzner et al., 2020; Turner, 2012; Turner et al., 2006).

Initial discussions across NDC ASPECTS work packages (WP1 capacity building workshop September 10th, 2021, the WP3 kick-off July 2021, and the WP3 workshop on harmonising the project's methodologies October 19th, 2021) have revealed the important role of various gender-related aspects for the sectoral workstreams of the NDC ASPECTS project. For the transport sector a lack of political engagement with potential violations of respectful limitations / deficiency of self-determination (see seventh dimension of the Gender Impact Assessment) is particularly pertinent. Unfortunately, existing statistical data is biased towards androcentrism. E.g., no (time series of) data is available on what proportion of car purchases and uses are the result of potential structural masculine violence in public space. However, "assaultive masculinity" dominating public spaces is considered to be highly relevant in terms of car purchase and use and respective emissions including with respect to preferences for SUVs.

The buildings sector is the sector which addresses – in an androcentric way: implicitly – the location of the care economy, where conditions for the gendered care economy and care work are determined. Therefore, the buildings sector is particularly relevant to gender.¹ Policy instruments that, e.g., do not guarantee rights of tenants to access affordable energy-saving rental housing, but instead increase energy prices, directly reduce the available income of households and thereby the budget for the care economy. Such instruments also disproportionately impact low-income households, not only because they affect a higher share of their income, but also because low-income households generally can only afford to live in less energy-efficient buildings. Households led by single mothers and female retirees make up disproportionately high shares of low-income households; energy price increases therefore typically exacerbate gender-based inequalities. Tax reliefs similarly exacerbate gender-based inequalities. As unpaid care and reproductive work is mostly undertaken by women while paid work is mostly undertaken by men, tax reliefs disproportionately benefit men, substantially endangering the potential for self-determination, freedom from dependence on men, and independent livelihood.

Recommendations for "behavioural" or "lifestyle" changes to reduce GHG emissions (and to compensate for increases in energy prices) such as vegetarian diets, managing energy use according to money-saving rather than care economic considerations etc. also mostly impact the gender-based externalised economy and women, as women are still in many households primarily responsible for care work. Moreover, such mitigation options are often associated with a need for more time to complete care

¹ Androcentrism tends to separate products or physis from their social, societal and gender contexts, also in constructing its term and categories; even though the care economy is the basis of society and households are the economies' primary economic actors, the care economy is not classified as an economic sector in standard terminologies, and households' economic activities are divided up among the buildings and transport sectors.

work - at the expense of the very population that has the smallest time budgets for personal use. For example, a study in Sweden showed that air-drying of laundry instead of using an energy-intensive dryer required more work, which was mostly not done by men, but by women (Carlsson-Kanyama & Lindén, 2007). Similarly, 80% of sufficiency measures that were initially developed in a gender-blind manner turned out to be gender-hierarchical in this sense (Spitzner & Buchmüller, 2016). Such mitigation options thus directly contradict policy obligations to reduce gender inequalities, but rather force the risk of exacerbating gender inequalities. The underlying “logic” of such approaches is to shift responsibility away from the political system (macro-level) towards the supposed ‘individual’ (micro-) and the supposed ‘private’ care economy (meso-level), thus disrespecting the disproportionate definition- and shaping power of care-givers over infrastructural, care-economical conditions. Recommendations for “behavioural” or “lifestyle” changes to reduce GHG emissions therefore often incorporate androcentric biases by implicitly calling for “care style” changes. However, if approached from a gender-responsive perspective, recommendations for “care style” changes can be useful to reduce GHG emissions: Care economically responsible policies would be able to adequately distinguish price structures according to care necessity and non-care avoidability, shift priorities between the respective alternative infrastructure systems of a sector, etc.

A key challenge for addressing gender equality in the context of climate and energy policy is the prevalence of the “polluter pays principle” particularly in the Anglo-American literature. The polluter pays principle assigns the responsibility for emissions (and energy consumption) to those responding to induced demand for mobility and/or energy including for care and reproductive work. In German (and some other European languages) the closest corresponding concept to the polluter pays principle is the “Verursacherprinzip” which literally translates to causer or responsibility principle. This notion more adequately addresses the question of who or what generates the need for mobility and energy. Who is responsible if goods and services for everyday needs are not available or accessible within easy car- and vehicle-free reach for all citizens in all city quarters and in all rural areas or can be procured in a time-efficient manner by public transport (modelling category: reachability of everyday relevant localities, care relevant infrastructures and reproductive relevant services)? Instead, the polluter pays principle would problematically point to the household, i.e. the care-giver, who needs to use a car to cope with inaccessibility and non-reachability to satisfy basic needs of himself/herself and others (modelling category: driven vehicle kilometres).² Ultimately, the focus on the responsibility of the “polluter” can lead to a situation where the root cause of the generation of emissions is not addressed. Instead, focussing only on “end-of-the-pipe” phenomena would impose an additional burden on households and care-givers and crucially leave the underlying structural problems unresolved politically.

Finally, energy-intensive industries feature a particularly high prevalence of gender-based divisions of labor. Women are often precluded from access to secure and well-paid jobs in industries and related service sectors while having to shoulder the major share of unpaid domestic care work (UNIDO, 2019). In particular moving to a circular economy entails opportunities for increasing industrial employment of women, but it also entails risks of increasing workloads for societally gender-hierarchically organised domestic care work, for example by the need to dispose of waste in a way that enables reuse and recycling (Pla-Julián & Guevara, 2019). Schultz (1993) demonstrated, studying empirically waste management contexts, that un-revised androcentric environmental policies engage in a high degree of

² The confusion of the “polluter pays principle” vs. the “causer principle” is also rooted in Anglo-American state philosophy which has no concept of common weal (in antique Greek tradition “Staat als Gemeinwesen”) unlike the continental European state philosophy of state provision of public services (“Daseinsvorsorge”).

"feminization of environmental responsibility". The same was proved in the global economy context (Wichterich, 1993) as well as for the transport sector (Spitzner, 2005; Spitzner & Beik, 1995). Therefore, the principle of explicit precaution against feminization of climate responsibility has been elevated to an essential component of sustainable thus gender responsible climate sector policies.

3 Generic Process of the Sectoral Conversations

The Sectoral Conversations are conceived as a series of sector-specific transdisciplinary mutual learning formats amongst a small, but targeted and carefully selected group of NDC ASPECTS researchers and external stakeholders within a sectoral system that co-produce knowledge and builds relationships over the project lifetime.

Figure 1: Pert-diagram of the WP1 work programme.

For each conversation cycle we will go through three phases:

- › **Preparation:** Identify the purpose and objectives for the conversation cycle and select adequate engagement methods to achieve those objectives. Logistical preparation.
- › **Sectoral conversation encounter:** The actual in-person meeting will take place back-to-back with project meetings. In order to maintain a high level of engagement also between the main events of the Sectoral Conversations, it will be required to engage with the participants regularly to ensure continuous communication, to solicit feedback in order to improve the participant experience in subsequent iterations, and to manage participants' expectations. Finally, this stage includes the substantive and logistical organization of the main events of the Sectoral Conversations including venues, catering as well as supporting travel arrangements of external participants (visa applications, reimbursement of expenses etc.)

- › **Digest and reflection of the sectoral conversation:** The objective of this stage is to facilitate the exploitation of the insights emerging from the Sectoral Conversations by WP2 to WP6 teams. This will include a project internal debrief of each conversation cycle involving all relevant sectoral experts involved in the subsequent work packages with a view to drawing specific conclusions on what is relevant for each of the other WPs, involving the work package leads in regard to reflecting the methodological foundation and proceeding in the work packages in the light of the additional insights gained, as well as a digest from the perspective of selected countries as appropriate. These insights will be documented and included in subsequent versions of the PDD. The documentation will (1) specify substantive lessons learned; (2) identify needs to adjust/refine research questions, assumptions, or research design in other WPs; and (3) identify key insights that have emerged, which contribute to new knowledge and may be of interest to sector stakeholders and national policymakers in the context of NDC and LTS development. Moreover, this stage will also include a debriefing of the process of the previous conversation engagement. On the basis of this reflection, the purpose and objectives as well as the engagement methods for the subsequent conversation cycle will be refined and updated.

Figure 2: Illustration of the Sectoral Conversations work flow.

We take note that one of the downsides of the sectoral approach proposed and implemented in the sectoral conversations is a risk to overlook cross-sectoral implications. The four sectors in focus are not independent of each other but coupled either directly or via the energy conversion sector. This sector coupling relates for example to the role of biomass produced in the AFOLU sector but used as a construction material in the building sector, a feedstock in the pulp and paper or even plastics industry, or a fuel in the energy conversion sector. In order to not lose track of those sector couplings, the debrief and digest of the sectoral conversations will explicitly also consider ways in which the discussed mitigation strategies and options could have ripple effects each of the other sectors as well as major implications for the energy conversion sector.

3.1 Groundwork: the development of the Conversation's Process Design Document

To have a fruitful conversation, it is required to start by outlining options and discussing the motivation and proposed design of the Sectoral Conversation across the three cycles. The Process Design Document (PDD) has been designed as a key instrument to support this thinking process.

Completing the PDD will certainly imply the need to narrow down the scope of the sectoral conversation to a limited number of specific transformation challenges and/or specific challenges and opportunities. This discussion of pros and cons for different options should be a process, involving different people at different levels, with the final details of the design being decided and agreed upon by the community gathered at the first conversation encounter. When preparing the first session, it is critical to achieve a balance between concrete propositions (to have a solid foundation for discussions) and openness (to allow participants to choose *their* topic and develop the necessary ownership). To prepare the ground for this choice of focus, a pre-scoping exercise is recommended (see Pre-scoping section below).

The PDD is intended to be a living document that will be iteratively updated. Different versions can also serve to track progress and the evolution of our discussions throughout the project. Preliminary versions of the PDDs are included as an annex to this deliverable. The submitted version contains more detailed plans for the first conversation cycle, but only generic information on the purpose and objectives of the second and third conversation cycle. After each sectoral conversation encounter, we will reflect the outcome both with respect to the content of the discussions as well as the process and functioning of the group. These reflections will also be documented in the PDD.

Building on the lessons and insights from the first (or second) conversation cycle, we will revise and specify the planning for subsequent conversation cycles and record those plans in updated versions of the PDD.

That way, the PDD serves as the central place for documenting the sectoral conversations. It will also allow us to trace our learning experience and serve as important data input for the subsequent Deliverable 1.2 "Report and academic article manuscript on Sectoral Conversations methodology".

For the initial development of the PDD, two main considerations are worth noting as part of the groundwork.

3.1.1 Building the sectoral conversation community

The selection of stakeholders that will be included in each of the sectoral conversation communities should first and foremost be aligned with the ultimate goal of the Sectoral Conversation. Matching the desirable outcome of the conversation and the actors that are required to reach this goal is a central and iterative process of the development (and further refinement) of the PDD. Moreover, there are a number of guiding principles that should inform the selection of stakeholders in accordance with the terms described in the project proposal. These are described below.

Sectoral Conversation participants shall be selected to (1) facilitate the exploitation of the newly generated knowledge in the NDCs and LEDS national processes and in the Global Stocktake (representation of national policymakers and key policy influencers); (2) cater for the transdisciplinary nature of the knowledge co-produced (representation of key stakeholders that are directly affected and have

the capacity to act as change agents within their respective sectoral systems); (3) provide good geographic representation from the project's targeted countries, and more specifically, on large emerging economies and a variety of EU countries, for which the Consortium counts on partner representation (Tier 1 countries). Gender balance and gender-related expertise will also be considered in the built-up of this community.

The Sectoral Conversations will flexibly include face-to-face workshops as well as ongoing decentralized engagement through e.g. online meetings, e-mail exchanges or other innovative remote meeting options. To ensure a high degree of engagement and building of trust, we aim for **~15 participants** for each Sectoral Conversation as well as continuous involvement of the same experts across all main encounters. We have budgeted to reimburse and compensate up to 10 external participants for each sector (5 from Europe and 5 non-European participants). Corresponding budget has been allocated to the sectoral leads.

Depending on the evolution of the discussions, additional stakeholders or specialized experts may be invited to join the group.

Ultimately, the responsibility for identifying and recruiting external participants lies with the sectoral conversation leads. A stakeholder mapping can help to identify key aspects and ensure a balanced representation as per the requirements outlined above.

For information purposes, a separate contact list should be maintained. To facilitate the GDPR conformity of the storage of personal data, the Wuppertal Institute will set up an online form to collect and store the contact details of external participants on a secure GDPR-compliant file sharing platform. This also allows us to delete the corresponding personal data after the completion of the project. The database can then be accessed by members of the consortium to generate issue-specific lists of recipients for distribution of sector-specific communications. It may also be used for general dissemination activities under WP7.

3.1.2 Pre-scoping

The pre-scoping should help sector leads in the choice of focus by integrating views of colleagues and external experts on the most recent developments and testing general appetite for further work on a specific topic/sub-sector/issue.

The pre-scoping phase should start as soon as possible and will be considered completed with the start of the first sectoral conversation in December 2021. All the inputs will be informing the development of the first version of this PDD and further refinements.

The talks with external stakeholders will help understand the interest and demand for discussion on specific areas within the real world actors, as well as identifying synergies and overlaps with other relevant initiatives. It will also be an important occasion to map networks and relationships to assess the possibility of reaching out to certain stakeholders. In fact, the capacity to convene the most relevant actors for a certain discussion will also determine the choice of focus for that conversation.

The talks with the Consortium colleagues will provide invaluable insight on the most critical focus areas per sector based on research undertaken to date. These exchanges will be most useful to understand the capacity of our Consortium to provide relevant research to a certain question, particularly noting the multidisciplinary nature of the team. The objective is to appraise where our Consortium can bring

best value in the face of a large number of challenges and gaps that need to be overcome to achieve the structural transformations underpinning the Paris-compatible pathways.

These exploratory exchanges are the responsibility of the sector conversation leads. Below we offer some ideas on how they could be organized. The PDD document also includes a proposed framework to capture the outputs of this “Pre-scoping” exercise.

Consultations with external stakeholders

- › Select a set of 4-6 external experts and/or sector stakeholders
 - › These interviews do not need to follow academic conventions. It may be just an informal structured dialogue.
 - › Consider including relevant members of the advisory board
 - › Consider a balance of perspectives: i.e., private, policy, civil society, as well as national and multinational levels
- › Structure in a consistent way the inputs of the stakeholder, for instance, according to challenges and solutions:
 - › The main challenges of the sector in order to move towards a deep decarbonization
 - › Relevant decarbonization options (e.g., technologies, policies, infrastructural changes, investments, behavioural/demand patterns) for advancing the deep decarbonization of the sector
- › Procure a traceable output:
 - › Summarizing notes of each talk

Consultations with Consortium colleagues

Note that you will have an opportunity to present preliminary ideas of your PDD to some of your Consortium colleagues during the ‘WP1 capacity building workshop’ (tentatively scheduled for September). This is likely to be attended by all WP leads and teams involved in the organization of the Sectoral Conversations.

Nevertheless, specific consultations and exchanges with colleagues are recommended, particularly to cover in depth expectations and/or needs from specific tasks across WPs related to your sectoral conversation. This may also take the form of a short online survey (potentially extended to a few “friends of the project” from our networks). This could include the following generic questions, or any specific question the sector leads may have in mind:

- › Based on existing knowledge: 1) Main critical deep decarbonization challenges, 2) Key components for deep decarbonization pathways (options) and 3) Critical “boundary condition” or enablers
- › For planned research: What are the key insights and/or assumptions of your research work within your WP that you would like to be discussed/triangulated by real-world stakeholders? (Besides challenges and options), that might help to set the scene of the conversation?

The results from the Consortium inputs may be structured according to the subjects mentioned (e.g., specific decarbonization challenges, decarbonization strategies or options, or related aspects). It may also be pertinent to highlight particular points of divergence/conflict arising from the interviews/survey.

3.2 Engagement Methods Toolkit

In this section a selection of engagement methods are presented and described that could be used to facilitate discussion in the Sectoral Conversations. The Sectoral Leads may decide whether to use these methods and – if necessary – adapt them to their specific needs.

The “conceptual clarification” method and the Three Horizons Framework were also tried and tested in practice at the WP1 kick-off meeting and the Sectoral Conversations capacity building workshop respectively.

Note that this section will, in all likelihood, be expanded in the future catering to the needs of the sectoral leads as the conversation progresses.

3.2.1 Conceptual clarification

Conceptual clarification is a method that aims at building agreement on the meaning and use of concepts, among a group of individuals that represent and/or enact different disciplines or expertises within a transdisciplinary research group.

“Concepts are mental symbols, the units of thought.” (Carey, 2011) Concepts are the essential building blocks of the descriptions, explanations and/or theories that any discipline or profession uses and processes in order to build valid statements about the behavior of the empirical world they focus on. Two features of concepts are particularly important to consider when advancing collaborative research. (a) The actual ‘content’ or ‘meaning’ of concepts: Concepts can be understood as mental representations of entities or phenomena that we observe, perceive and/or pretend to apprehend. (b) The relation between concepts (as mental symbols) with terms (i.e. linguistic symbols): This implies on the one hand that concepts (and the entities they represent) are linked to ‘labels’ (words) and on the other hand that most of the operations we undertake with concepts (like thinking, explaining or speaking) are facilitated by the use of language.

One central differentiation among disciplines (and among professions) is that they develop their own set of concepts, explanations and theories in rather autonomous ways. Therefore, in settings of collaborative research there is not any guarantee for the convergence among the relations between concepts (mental representations) and actual meanings applied by the different disciplines and professions involved, even in the case (or particularly when) the same terms (words, linguistic symbols) are used. This can be critical in the case of concepts that are central for the definition of the research endeavour; for instance in the case of notions that are key for building the problem definition, the objectives, the guiding questions and/or the framing of the research. Clarifying those differences and agreeing on ways to deal with them is particularly important in the early stages of the research process (Bergmann et al., 2012).

3.2.2 Instructions

Conceptual clarification among different disciplines and expertise is facilitated through the sequential realization of three stages:

- › Explicit articulation of individual understandings: The aim of the first stage is to foster the individual reflection on the understandings that each individual applies to the concept in question. The main output expected from this process is the explicit articulation of key features of one's own meaning
- › Set different understandings in relation: Once individual meanings become explicit and understandable, the second stage fosters the exchange and comparison of those features that make up the different understandings of the same concept. Particular attention is set on recognizing similarities, complementarities and contradictions.
- › Building agreement: The aim of the final stage is to reach an agreement on how to operate with the concept within the research project. This can be facilitated by building a definition of the concept that: (a) allows each of the involved disciplines and expertises to engage with the concept, even if not fully reflecting their own 'original' understanding of it and (b) explicitly points at contradictions or controversial issues that were recognized as critical in the previous stages.

Conceptual clarification can be facilitated through a process comprising the following four steps:

- 1) Individual Reflection: Each participant writes down up to 5 keywords/short-phrases that he/she associates with the concept in question. To facilitate the further steps it is recommendable to use one card for each keyword. [recommended time: 2-3 minutes]
- 2) Bilateral dialogue: Pairs are built. Each person explains her/his own understanding of the concept in question to the partner by presenting his/her own cards and clarifying the keywords on them. The aim is twofold: (a) to reach a mutual understanding of the meanings that each person ascribes to the concept and (b) to identify similarities, complementarities or contradictions among the keywords shared. The cards are organized (clustered) according to their similarities. New cards are created in order to label those clusters of keywords that are particularly similar or tightly related. Additionally, controversial issues are identified and if necessary also labeled in a new card. [recommended time: 15 minutes]
- 3) Group dialogue - clustering: Groups of 5 to 7 persons are built. Each person selects up to three cards resulting from the bilateral dialogue: Up to two cards linked to clusters or issues where accordance or similarities were recognized and at least one card linked to controversial issues. Similarly to the previous step the group dialogue has a twofold aim: (a) to reach mutual understanding of the different issues associated with the concept, but in this case not from an individual perspective, but from a perspective enriched through the previous bilateral dialogues. (b) To identify similarities, complementarities or contradictions among the shared issues. Similar to the previous step the cards are organized according to their similarities or interlinkages. The output of the dialogue is a sort of conceptual mapping, in which the distribution of the cards reflect the relations (similarities, interconnections and/or controversies) recognized among the issues that have been discussed. [recommended time: 20 - 30 minutes]
- 4) Group dialogue - synthesizing: The aim of this step is to produce a definition of the concept in question that articulates the different issues discussed and recognized in the previous steps. For that aim each of the groups built in step 3 write a definition based on the conceptual

mapping they generated in the previous step. Besides elaborating on issues that were recognized as similar or interlinked, the definition should also integrate or explicitly recognize those issues that remained controversial. [recommended time: 20 - 30 minutes]

Depending on the size of the team involved in the conceptual clarification exercise it might be recommendable to build more than one group for step 3 and 4. In that case a fifth step should be considered, in which each group has the possibility to present and discuss its results with the whole team.

3.2.3 Three Horizons

The Three Horizons Dialogue framework (Sharpe et al., 2016) is a tool to engage a diverse group of stakeholders in a structured collective imagining/visioning exercise. Its key strength is to integrate diverse perspectives and to enable a constructive way forward even when competing or contradicting views are assembled in the group.

The method is particularly useful as a brainstorming tool for initiating the Sectoral Conversations. However, it can also be used in a more in-depth way, guiding an entire scenario-development workshop. In the Sectoral Conversations this method could be used on the occasion of the first encounter as it enables the group to quickly establish a common ground from which decisions for the direction of future deliberations in the group can be taken.

3.2.3.1 Instructions

These instructions are paraphrased from Sharpe et al. (2016).

Figure 3: Illustration of the three horizons process. Source: Adapted from Sharpe et al (2016).

FIRST HORIZON: WHAT IS (WRONG WITH) THE CURRENT SECTORAL SYSTEM?

H1 represents the way things are done now, generally called “business as usual.” H1 patterns are starting to lose fit with emerging conditions. This corresponds to ‘system knowledge’. “Keeping the lights on” in the current system requires a management perspective.

THIRD HORIZON: WHAT DOES A DECARBONIZED AND SUSTAINABLE SECTORAL SYSTEM LOOK LIKE?

H3 represents the emerging pattern that will be the long-term successor to the current first horizon. It is appearing and growing on the fringes of the present system. This corresponds to ‘target knowledge’. Imagining the third horizon requires a visionary mindset.

SECOND HORIZON: WHAT ARE THE THINGS THAT HELP US TRANSFORM?

H2 is the turbulent domain of transitional activities and innovations that people are trying out in response to the changing landscape between the first and third horizons. This corresponds to ‘transformation knowledge’. Bringing new ideas and innovations into reality requires entrepreneurial spirit.

Five Steps:

- 1) Examining present concerns: In which ways are current practices losing fit?
- 2) Exploring future aspirations: What are the key elements (technologies, practices, values) that we are envisioning for a decarbonized and sustainable sector?
- 3) Exploring inspirational practice in the present: What are “pockets of the future in the present”?
- 4) Which innovations are in play that may connect the present to the future? Are these innovations transformative (H2+) and leading to the realization of H3? Or are they rather propping up the existing system (H2-)?
- 5) Which essential features of the present ought to be maintained in the future?

For each step use color-coded post-its to capture your ideas in each step and cluster them at the corresponding area of the figure!

3.2.4 Futures Wheel

The purpose of the futures wheel method is to assess possible implications of proposed changes in a systematic and holistic way. Starting from an assumption about future change, a first order of direct effects is explored. Then second and subsequently third order ripple effects are also considered. That way a group of experts can relatively quickly grasp anticipated implications (good or bad) for any proposed action.

In the context of the NDC ASPECTS Sectoral Conversations, this method is particularly apt to interrogate proposed solutions (decarbonization strategies and associated policies and measures) and their respective technical, social, economic and political/institutional implications. This method can be recommended for the second round of sectoral conversations.

3.2.4.1 Instructions

The instructions are paraphrased from Benckendorff (2008) and Defila et al. (2018).

Figure 4 Illustration of Futures Wheel. Source: Benckendorff (2008).

The futures wheel is a diagram with a series of concentric circles. Each circle corresponds to a subsequent order of ripple effects. To develop the diagram participants will have to complete a three-stage process:

- 1) Develop the scenario for which implications ought to be assessed. It is critical that all participants have a sufficiently clear and shared understanding of what is being discussed. The scenario (or a representation thereof as a key word) is placed at the center of the diagram.
- 2) First order or principle impacts are being explored that are direct effects of the implementation of the scenario. Each first order impact is represented as a new node in a concentric circle around the starting point scenario.
- 3) Second order impacts are discussed for each of the first order impacts identified. Again, these second order impacts are represented as new nodes on a new concentric circle, each connected to the first order impact from which it was triggered. This approach can be repeated for third and fourth order impacts etc., if necessary.

After completing all levels of the Future Wheel, the participants have a clear picture of possible direct and indirect consequences, as well as spill-over effects/synergies among these consequences, resulting from the change identified in the beginning. On that basis, participants can generate a list of positive and negative consequences of the proposed action which, in turn, can serve as a starting point for a risk-analysis (for the bad consequences) or for thinking how to take advantage or positive consequences.

3.2.5 Tools & Means

Aside from using different engagement methods to foster the discussion between the participants, there are other types of “tools” or resources that can be used while organizing the Sectoral Conversations. We started to list some with the aim of providing ideas to the organizers of the conversations. This list can be completed or made longer in the duration of the project.

3.2.5.1 [Mailing List](#)

The Sectoral Conversations do not have to be limited to an annual gathering. They can also be an opportunity to engage with a community of practice, share ideas, discuss some specific topics in between sessions, etc. Therefore, sectoral leads could create a common mailing list, or any other communication tool they like, where to share ideas, continue discussions or forward interesting resources.

Data management and GDPR-compliance should be taken into account when organizing these communication channels. To gather personal data, sectoral leads will use a centralized online form that has been created to register and keep track of the participants of the Sectoral Conversation, as detailed also below.

3.2.5.2 [Virtual Workshops](#)

Following the same spirit as above, smaller virtual gatherings can be organized in between the sessions. The sectoral leads could take leadership in proposing these interim meetings, although they could also be proposed by the members of the Sectoral Conversation. The purpose of these meetings could be discussing specific issues, finishing work or discussions that were not closed in the formal session, or to plan the Sectoral Conversation itself.

3.2.5.3 [Common contact book](#)

For information purposes, a separate contact list will be maintained. To facilitate the GDPR conformity of the storage of personal data, the Wuppertal Institute will set up an online form to collect and store the contact details of external participants on a secure GDPR-compliant file sharing platform. This also allows deleting the corresponding personal data after the completion of the project. The database can then be accessed by members of the consortium to generate issue-specific lists of recipients for distribution of sector-specific communications. It may also be used for general dissemination activities under WP7.

3.2.5.4 [Use of professional facilitators](#)

A very important tool in the Sectoral Conversations, which will include many different actors and views, could be the use of a professional facilitator. Facilitators plan, guide and manage a group to ensure that the group's objectives are met effectively, with clear thinking, good participation and full buy-in from everyone who is involved. Facilitators, therefore, could help stir the process and have more inclusive decisions. Hiring a facilitator is subject to budget availability.

3.2.5.5 Media

The result of the sectoral conversations may be in many shapes and forms. It could be a publication, an intervention, a paper... Sectoral leads, as well as sectoral conversation participants, could consider integrating media in the outputs. That could be, for example, a newspaper article that explains the results, a video that highlights the process, an infographic that summarizes the findings... The conversations themselves will be under Chatham House rules, but public outcomes could be discussed in advance to accommodate the needs and concerns of the participants.

3.2.6 Logistics and Media

Tasks 1.2-1.5 include the substantive and logistical organization of the main events of the Sectoral Conversations including venues, catering as well as supporting travel arrangements of external participants, including visa applications, reimbursement of expenses, etc.

The first Sectoral Conversations will be organized online due to the COVID-19 pandemic, therefore making logistics and administration easier. However, some logistics and admin basics still need to be taken into account even when the event happens online:

- 1) **Sending invites:** Please identify the people you want to participate in the Sectoral Conversations with sufficient time, in order to be able to secure their presence in the conversation. For an online meeting, a 1-month notice could be appropriate.
- 2) **Choosing an online platform:** Make sure you choose an online platform (such as Zoom; Meet, etc) that serves the needs you may have. For example, if you need breakout groups, polls, subtitles, etc. Different platforms may offer different functionalities.
- 3) **Considering schedules across time zones:** One of the setbacks of online meetings is the more reduced day time when different time zones overlap. Please take into account the time zones where the participants of the sectoral conversations are in, in order to secure a meaningful engagement. Generally speaking, 1-3pm European time works as a good overlap between Asian and American time zones. Adapting to these specificities may reduce the time you have per day, needed to spread the conversation between more days than expected.
- 4) **Keeping engagement online:** Running an online meeting is more than simply switching on your camera. It requires deeper engagement to keep participants' attention, built-in moments where to have a more human connection, or being mindful of different levels of technology knowledge. You can find [here](#) further reflections and tips.

4 Glossary

The Consortium found it very important that common definitions are shared amongst its members. A decision was made to build a collaborative Glossary, where definitions will be built that represent the complexity and understanding of the group. For now, we have listed some definitions of key concepts taking the IPCC Glossary as a starting point, but these will be edited and improved over the duration of the project. Therefore, this glossary will expand and evolve as we continue to work with the guidebook and PDDs.

Key concepts:

Narratives: Qualitative descriptions of plausible future world evolutions, describing the characteristics, general logic and developments underlying a particular quantitative set of scenarios. Narratives are also referred to in the literature as ‘storylines’.

Pathways: The temporal evolution of natural and/or human systems towards a future state. Pathway concepts range from sets of quantitative and qualitative scenarios or narratives of potential futures to solution-oriented decision-making processes to achieve desirable societal goals. Pathway approaches typically focus on biophysical, techno-economic, and/or socio-behavioural trajectories and involve various dynamics, goals and actors across different scales.

Model: “A model makes precise assumptions about a limited set of parameters and variables that compose a theory. Logic, mathematics, game theory, experimentation and simulation, and other means are used to systematically explore the consequences of these assumptions in a limited set of outcomes” (Ostrom et al., 2014, p. 269).

In the context of NDC ASPECTS, climate models are a numerical representation of the climate system based on the physical, chemical and biological properties of its components, their interactions and feedback processes, and accounting for some of its known properties. The climate system can be represented by models of varying complexity; that is, for any one component or combination of components a spectrum or hierarchy of models can be identified, differing in such aspects as the number of spatial dimensions, the extent to which physical, chemical or biological processes are explicitly represented, or the level at which empirical parameterizations are involved. There is an evolution towards more complex models with interactive chemistry and biology. Climate models are applied as a research tool to study and simulate the climate and for operational purposes, including monthly, seasonal and interannual climate predictions.

Decarbonization: The process by which countries, individuals or other entities aim to achieve zero fossil carbon existence. Typically refers to a reduction of the carbon emissions associated with electricity, industry and transport.

Sectoral System: Sectoral systems provide identifiable societal functions such as transport, electricity, raw materials or built living and care working places. They are constituted of ensembles of actors (corporations, administrative bodies, political groups/parties, international organizations), (gendered) societal definition and shaping power structures, care and accumulation economic structures, infrastructures and technologies, institutions and ideas that produce degrees of path dependency and resistance to change.

Sector coupling refers to the interconnection of two or more sectoral systems first and foremost via the energy conversion sector. A prime example is the electrification of heating, mobility and industrial production.

Transdisciplinarity entails an aspiration “(a) to grasp the relevant complexity of a problem (b) to take into account the diversity of life-world and scientific perceptions of problems, (c) to link abstract and case-specific knowledge, and (d) develop knowledge and practices that promote what is perceived to be the common good” (Hirsch Hadorn et al., 2008, p. 4). Transdisciplinary research brings together a wide range of academic disciplines – in the case of NDC ASPECTS political science, economics, social science, engineering, law, natural sciences (biology, physics), mathematical modelling – and engages deeply with stakeholders to co-design the research questions, co-produce results, and co-create specific recommendations. Transdisciplinarity requires exploring the complementarities but also confront contradictions of different disciplinary perspectives. This engagement may enhance the social and cultural robustness of the generated knowledge, i.e. knowledge that can be understood, processed and applied by all parties involved (Nowotny et al., 2001), and knowledge accounting for uncertainties and the ambiguities linked to it (Vilsmaier 2017).

Transformation: A change in the fundamental attributes of natural and societal systems.

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